

**Final Report for the Collaborative Research Center
(SFB – Transregio 142)**

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**Tailored nonlinear photonics:
From fundamental concepts to
functional structures**

Spokesperson

Prof. Dr. Thomas Zentgraf
Paderborn University
Faculty of Science
Department of Physics
Warburger Str. 100
33098 Paderborn

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1 Summary / Zusammenfassung

The CRC-TRR 142 research center pursued a central strategy of engineering nonlinear optical properties through both materials and structured photonic environments on micro- and nanoscales. The research combined three interconnected areas: Fundamentals and Light-Matter Interaction, Materials and Technology, and Functional Structures and Quantum Applications. During the first funding period, the consortium demonstrated its core strategic idea by combining nonlinear optics, nanostructured semiconductors, advanced spectroscopy, and ab initio theory to control light at the level of single photons, polaritons, and excitons. The second period significantly advanced control of nonlinear light-matter interaction in nanostructured semiconductors for quantum photonics, with themes including ultrafast control of excitons, polaritons, and phonons. The third period focused on extended parameter ranges, material suitability for new concepts, and realization of demonstrator quantum systems.

One major focus was developing advanced quantum-dot based quantum light sources and hybrid systems combining different platforms on single chips. A transfer printing toolbox for device stacking and integrated superconducting detectors were developed. For ideal photon pair generation at telecom frequencies, local droplet etching was adapted to quantum dots emitting in the optical C-band. Another goal was establishing thin-film lithium niobate technology suitable for quantum photonic integrated circuits, capable of producing high-quality structures and low-loss devices for optical down-conversion. We succeeded in establishing high-quality technology and demonstrated integrated two-photon interference experiments and two-color parametric down-conversion sources.

The CRC introduced a fundamentally new scheme for single-photon generation from semiconductor quantum dots, based on partially stimulated two-photon emission from the biexciton state. Using a classical control laser to define a virtual intermediate state inside the bandgap, the scheme enables all-optically tunable single-photon sources with high flexibility in tailoring photon characteristics. We also developed robust optical protocols using four-wave mixing with eight light fields to control exciton dephasing and photon echo timing, establishing powerful tools for ultrafast, all-optical timing control of collective quantum states in solids. Ultrafast electrical-signal sampling using single quantum dots as optoelectronic probes achieved millivolt voltage sensitivity and temporal resolution better than twenty picoseconds.

For polariton systems, we engineered beam amplifiers that increase intensity without deflection by balancing excitonic and photonic potentials. Controlled generation of vortex modes and ultrafast control was demonstrated in polariton condensates, where an ultrashort off-resonant pulse can reverse vortex rotation direction, realizing transient optical bits controllable on ultrafast timescales. Measurement time for quantum state correlation was reduced from thirty minutes to less than a millisecond through consistent optimization.

Furthermore, we explored interaction of ultrafast acoustic strain pulses with optically active quantum emitters, finding picosecond strain pulses can dramatically modify quantum dot emission. Here, we achieved ultimate optical detection sensitivity for propagating coherent phonons in semiconductor superlattices, detecting minimal displacements of only 100 attometres. In addition, we studied nonlinear metamaterials with continuously tunable phase of nonlinear polarizability that enabled complete control of harmonic wave propagation within ultrathin surfaces, forming the basis for nonlinear holography and information multiplexing.

For the important material system lithium niobate, advanced ab initio methods revealed a fundamental band gap of approximately 5.9 electron volts and spin textures not previously appreciated. Atomistic structures of polarons were resolved for the first time, and bound polaron formation was modeled at approximately 60 femtoseconds at room temperature.

For quantum interfaces, dispersion-engineered sum-frequency conversion in periodically poled lithium niobate waveguides achieved over 60 percent internal conversion efficiency with 7.5-fold bandwidth compression. During the last funding period, a quantum pulse gate concept enabled measurement capabilities beyond classical limits for estimating time separation of closely spaced pulses. Electric-field poling technology achieved domain periods down to 1.0 micrometers for spectrally and temporally uncorrelated photon pairs. Finally, we demonstrated coherent manipulation of quantum dot states using purely electrical control on ultrafast timescales via the Stark effect, significantly broadening the toolbox for controlling solid-state qubits and paving the way for integrated optoelectronic-quantum devices.

2 Published results

2.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance (50 selected)

- [1] „**Integrated transition edge sensors on titanium in-diffused lithium niobate waveguides**“, Höpker, J.P., Gerrits, T., Lita, A., Krapick, S., Herrmann, H., Ricken, R., Quiring, V., Mirin, R., Nam, S.W., Silberhorn, C., & Bartley, T.J., *APL Photonics*, 2019, 10.1063/1.5086276.
- [2] „**Vortex Multistability and Bessel Vortices in Polariton Condensates**“, Ma, X. & Schumacher, S., *Physical Review Letters*, 2018, 10.1103/PhysRevLett.121.227404.
- [3] „**A quantum dot single-photon source with on-the-fly all-optical polarization control and timed emission**“, Heinze, D., Breddermann, D., Zrenner, A., & Schumacher, S., *Nature Communications*, 2015, 10.1038/ncomms9473.
- [4] „**Realization of all-optical vortex switching in exciton-polariton condensates**“, Ma, X., Berger, B., Aßmann, M., Driben, R., Meier, T., Schneider, C., Höfling, S., & Schumacher, S., *Nature Communications*, 2020, 10.1038/s41467-020-14702-5.
- [5] „**A multi-mode super-fano mechanism for enhanced third harmonic generation in silicon metasurfaces**“, Hähnel, D., Golla, C., Albert, M., Zentgraf, T., Myroshnychenko, V., Förstner, J., & Meier, C., *Light: Science and Applications*, 2023, 10.1038/s41377-023-01134-1.
- [6] „**Manipulating polariton condensates by Rashba-Dresselhaus coupling at room temperature**“, Li, Y., Ma, X., Zhai, X., Gao, M., Dai, H., Schumacher, S., & Gao, T., *Nature Communications*, 2022, 10.1038/s41467-022-31529-4.
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- [9] „**Nonlinear Wavefront Control by Geometric-Phase Dielectric Metasurfaces: Influence of Mode Field and Rotational Symmetry**“, Liu, B., Sain, B., Reineke, B., Zhao, R., Meier, C., Huang, L., Jiang, Y., & Zentgraf, T., *Advanced Optical Materials*, 2020, 10.1002/adom.201902050.
- [10] „**Second harmonic generation spectroscopy on hybrid plasmonic/dielectric nanoantennas**“, Linnenbank, H., Grynko, Y., Förstner, J., & Linden, S., *Light: Science and Applications*, 2016, 10.1038/LSA.2016.13.
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- [12] „**Scalability of parametric down-conversion for generating higher-order Fock states**“, Tiedau, J., Bartley, T.J., Harder, G., Lita, A.E., Nam, S.W., Gerrits, T., & Silberhorn, C., *Physical Review A*, 2019, 10.1103/PhysRevA.100.041802.
- [13] „**Tomography and Purification of the Temporal-Mode Structure of Quantum Light**“, Ansari, V., Donohue, J.M., Allgaier, M., Sansoni, L., Brecht, B., Roslund, J., Treps, N., Harder, G., & Silberhorn, C., *Physical Review Letters*, 2018, 10.1103/PhysRevLett.120.213601.
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- [15] „**Rotational Doppler effect in nonlinear optics**“, Li, G., Zentgraf, T., & Zhang, S., *Nature Physics*, 2016, 10.1038/nphys3699.

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- [25] „**LiNbO₃ surfaces from a microscopic perspective**“, Sanna, S. & Schmidt, W.G., *Journal of Physics Condensed Matter*, 2017, 10.1088/1361-648X/aa818d.
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- [37] „Control of the electron dynamics in solid-state high harmonic generation on ultrafast time scales by a polarization-skewed laser pulse“, Song, X., Yang, S., Wang, G., Lin, J., Wang, L., Meier, T., & Yang, W., *Optics Express*, 2023, 10.1364/OE.491418.
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- [39] „Defect complexes in congruent LiNbO₃ and their optical signatures“, Li, Y., Schmidt, W.G., & Sanna, S., *Physical Review B - Condensed Matter and Materials Physics*, 2015, 10.1103/PhysRevB.91.174106.
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- [44] „Toward Efficient Toxic-Gas Detectors: Exploring Molecular Interactions of Sarin and Dimethyl Methylphosphonate with Metal-Centered Phthalocyanine Structures“, Aldahhak, H., Powroźnik, P., Pander, P., Jakubik, W., Dias, F.B., Schmidt, W.G., Gerstmann, U., & Krzywiecki, M., *Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 2020, 10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b11116.
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3 List of projects

Project	Project Title	Research Area	Project Leader, Institution	Duration
A	Fundamentals / Light-Matter-Interaction			
A01	Two-photon emission in wide-gap semiconductors	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	M. Betz, TU Do C. Ruppert, TU Do	2014-2017
A02	Nonlinear optical pulse propagation in wide-gap semiconductors	Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys.	I. Akimov, TU Do T. Meier, UPB	2014-2025
A03	Two-photon physics with biexciton transitions	Theo. Phys. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	S. Schumacher, UPB A. Zrenner, UPB D. Reuter, UPB (2018-2021)	2014-2021
A04	Coherence and photon statistics of cavity polaritons in wide-gap semiconductors	Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys. Exp. Phys.	M. Assmann, TU Do S. Schumacher, UPB M. Bayer, TU Do (2014-2017)	2014-2025
A05	Plasmonic nano-antenna enhanced nonlinear light emission and frequency conversion in dielectric and semiconductor micro-structures	Exp. Phys. Theo. EE. Exp. Phys.	T. Zentgraf, UPB J. Förstner, UPB C. Meier, UPB	2014-2017
A06	Ultrafast acoustics modulation of light emission	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	M. Bayer, TU Do A. Scherbakov, TU Do (2022-2025) D. As, UPB (2014-2017) D. Reuter, UPB (2018-2025)	2014-2025
A07	Widely non-degenerate stimulated two-photon emission in semiconductors	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys.	C. Ruppert, TU Do M. Betz, TU Do T. Meier, UPB	2018-2021
A08	Nonlinear coupling of interlayer excitons in van der Waals heterostructures to plasmonic and dielectric nanocavities	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	M. Cinchetti, TU Do T. Zentgraf, UPB K. Jöns, UPB	2018-2025
A09	Three-photon state generation with on-chip pump suppression in topological waveguides	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	T. Zentgraf, UPB B. Brecht, UPB	2022-2025
A10	Nonlinear strong-field dynamics of atomically thin transition metal dichalcogenides	Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys.	C. Lange, TU Do T. Meier, UPB C. Ruppert, TU Do	2022-2025
A11	Control of excitonic optical harmonic generation by electric fields	Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys.	D. Yakovlev, TU Do U. Gerstmann, UPB	2022-2025
B	Materials and Technology			

B01	Nonlinear multi-photon and harmonics generation spectroscopy on ZnO-based nanostructures	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys.	C. Meier, UPB D. Yakovlev, TU Do E. Rauls, UPB	2014-2021
B02	Nonlinear optics and coherent intersubband physics of cubic GaN/Al(GaN) quantum well structures	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	D. As, UPB I. Akimov, TU Do M. Betz, TU Do	2014-2021
B03	Effect of extended and point defects on the ferroelectric and optical properties of LiNbO ₃	Theo. Phys. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	S. Sanna, UPB S. Greulich-Weber, UPB G. Berth, UPB	2014-2017
B04	Ab-initio theory for photonic materials	Theo. Phys. Theo. Phys. Theo. Phys.	W.G. Schmidt, UPB A. Schindlmayr, UPB U. Gerstmann, UPB (2018-2021)	2014-2021
B05	Tailored KTP and LiNbO ₃ waveguide structures for counter-propagating parametric down-conversion processes	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	G. Berth, UPB C. Silberhorn, UPB	2018-2021
B06	Ultrafast coherent opto-electronic control of a photonic quantum system	Theo. EE. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	J. Förstner, UPB K. Jöns, UPB D. Reuter, UPB	2022-2025
B07	Polaron signatures in the optical response of lithium niobate	Theo. Phys. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	W. G. Schmidt, UPB C. Eigner, UPB T. Bartley, UPB	2022-2025
B08	Subcycle nonlinearities of ultrastrong light-matter coupling	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	C. Lange, TU Do D. Reuter, UPB	2022-2025
B09	Quasi-bound states in the continuum for efficient second harmonic generation and spatial phase tailoring in GaAs metasurfaces	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	T. Zentgraf, UPB C. Meier, UPB	2022-2025
C Functional Structures / Quantum Applications				
C01	Direct measurement of time-frequency shaped ultrafast quantum pulses from parametric downconversion and upconversion processes	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	C. Silberhorn, UPB M. Bayer, TU Do	2014-2021
C02	Monolithic integration of a parametric down-conversion source and a two-photon interferometer	Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys. Theo. Phys.	C. Silberhorn, UPB T. Meier, UPB (2014-2017) P. Sharapova, UPB (2018-2021)	2014-2021
C03	Nonlinear optics in quantum dot molecules	Exp. Phys. Theo. EE.	A. Greulich, TU Do J. Förstner, UPB	2014-2018
C04	Ultrafast electric control of optical polarizations and transitions	Exp. Phys. EE. Theo. EE.	A. Zrenner, UPB A. Thiede, UPB J. Förstner, UPB (2018-2021)	2014-2021
C05	Nonlinear optical surfaces based on ZnO-plasmonic hybrid-nanostructures	Exp. Phys. Theo. EE. Exp. Phys.	T. Zentgraf, UPB J. Förstner, UPB C. Meier, UPB	2018-2021
C06	Integrated measurement-induced nonlinearity with superconducting detectors	Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys.	T. Bartley, UPB T. Meier, UPB	2018-2021
C07	Cavity-enhanced spontaneous parametric down-conversion with temporal filtering using integrated superconducting detectors	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	T. Bartley, UPB C. Silberhorn, UPB	2022-2025

C08	Hybrid lithium niobate on insulator quantum photonic integrated circuit	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys.	K. Jöns, UPB D. Reuter, UPB C. Silberhorn, UPB	2022-2025
C09	On-demand ideal photon pair generation for entanglement swapping at telecom frequencies	Exp. Phys. Exp. Phys. Theo. Phys.	K. Jöns, UPB D. Reuter, UPB S. Schumacher, UPB	2022-2025
C10	Generation and characterization of quantum light in nonlinear systems: A theoretical analysis	Theo. Phys. Theo. Phys.	P. Sharapova, UPB J. Sperling, UPB	2022-2025
C11	Compact high performance photon pair source using ultrafast hybrid modulators based on CMOS and LNOI	Exp. Phys. EE.	C. Silberhorn, UPB J.C. Scheytt, UPB	2022-2025
Z Service and Administration				
Z01	Molecular beam epitaxy of tailored GaAs-based heterostructures	Exp. Phys.	D. Reuter, UPB	2014-2021
Z02	Management of the Collaborative Research Center		A. Zrenner, UPB (2014-2021) C. Silberhorn, UPB (2022-2024) T. Zentgraf, UPB (2025)	2014-2025

4 Scientific development of the research center

A central strategy of the CRC was to engineer nonlinear optical properties not only via materials but also through structured photonic environments on micro- and nanoscales. For that three *Research Areas* were combined to cover different aspects of the research.

Research Area A: Fundamentals / Light-Matter-Interaction

Projects with focus on novel processes and effects of nonlinear physics covering:

- new phenomena based on *extended and extreme parameter ranges*
- *fundamental aspects* of nonlinear light-matter-interaction with strong nonlinearities
- *quantum character* of nonlinear interactions in structured materials

Research Area B: Materials and Technology

Projects with focus on technology or material design for nonlinear interactions covering:

- the *control of material properties* for nonlinear and quantum effects
- the *theoretical description* of nonlinear material properties
- the *suitability of materials* for new nonlinear concepts

Research Area C: Functional Structures / Quantum Applications

Projects with focus on functionalities of nonlinearities covering:

- the *analysis and quantification of nonlinear processes* and concepts for quantum applications
- the *scientific advancement of photonic quantum technology*
- the realization of first *demonstrator quantum systems*

During the first funding period of CRC/TRR 142, we demonstrated the core strategic idea of the consortium: to combine nonlinear optics, nanostructured semiconductors, advanced spectroscopy, and ab initio theory in order to control light at the level of single photons, polaritons, and excitons, and to engineer functional building blocks for future quantum photonic technologies. The second funding period has significantly advanced the control of nonlinear light-matter interaction in nanostructured semiconductors and its use for quantum photonics. Central themes were ultrafast control of excitons, polaritons, and phonons; tailoring nonlinear optical response via nanostructuring; and nonlinear quantum emitters and fast optoelectronics for advanced photon generation and measurement. Together, these results were preparing a stronger integration of semiconductor photonics and quantum optics during the third funding period, where new

phenomena based on extended and extreme parameter ranges as well as the suitability of materials for new nonlinear concepts were put in the focus. Furthermore, the scientific advancement of photonic quantum technology and the realization of first demonstrator quantum systems were targeted within the CRC.

One focus of our research was devoted towards the development of advanced quantum-dot based quantum light sources and hybrid systems, which combine the advantages of different platforms and can perform different tasks on one single chip. A transfer printing toolbox for device stacking as well as integrated superconducting detectors, which can be combined with cavity enhanced PDC, have been developed. For the implementation of ideal photon pair generation at telecom frequencies, local droplet etching has been adapted to quantum dots, which emit in the optical C-band. The theoretical work studied the impact of click detection for measuring photon statistics and also analysed in this context boson sampling as a promising candidate for photonic quantum computation. Moreover, entanglement in relativistic systems was researched as a key resource for quantum technologies.

Another goal of the CRC was the establishment of a thin-film lithium niobate technology (TFLN), which is suitable for quantum PICs. This implied that the technology needs to be capable of producing structures and low-loss devices of high quality. The work has proven to pose significant challenges on both, finding appropriate parameter settings for a highly optimized fabrication routines and gaining a deep understanding of the underlying physics and engineering principles. Yet, we succeeded in establishing a high-quality TFLN technology and could demonstrate the first two-photon interference experiment and two-color parametric downconversion (PDC) source. Using TFLN modulators we studied the performance of our compact, high frequency circuits for an efficient and highly controllable generation of pulsed light from CW lasers.

In the following, we will highlight a few key outcomes during the entire funding period of the CRC that progressed the research field and led to new discoveries.

Nonlinear quantum optics with semiconductor quantum dots and polaritons

The generation of well-defined on-demand photons is of high importance for future information technology. Within the CRC we introduced a fundamentally new scheme for single-photon generation from a semiconductor quantum dot (QD), based on a partially stimulated two-photon emission process from the biexciton state. The key idea is to use a classical control laser to define and drive a “virtual” intermediate state inside the bandgap. A coherent pump laser triggers emission of the first photon in a stimulated process into a virtual, non-resonant intermediate state in the bandgap. From this virtual state, the QD relaxes to its ground state and emits a second photon spontaneously, which is coupled into an optical cavity mode.

Because of energy and spin conservation, the properties of this second photon – the useful single photon – are directly linked to, and in a precise sense complementary to, the properties of the stimulating laser: its polarization and frequency can be controlled by the classical pump field. This scheme is conceptually similar to a nonlinear “down-conversion” or Raman-like process implemented at the level of a single emitter, and it opens a route to all-optically tunable single-photon sources in semiconductor platforms, with high flexibility in tailoring photon characteristics.

Here, the projects A03 and C04 combined epitaxial QD growth, nanofabrication, nonlinear spectroscopy, and theory to develop novel concepts. In our work, we pioneered a concept where a nonlinear stimulated down-conversion (SDC)-like process is used to control single-photon emission: Starting from the biexciton state $|B\rangle$, a tunable classical control laser defines a virtual intermediate state in a stimulated process. From this virtual state, spontaneous emission leads to the ground state $|G\rangle$, emitting a single photon whose energy and polarization are determined by the control field. This establishes a new class of nonlinear, quantum-optical single-emitter devices where classical control fields shape quantum emission.

In strongly inhomogeneously broadened ensembles of quantum dots (QDs), exciton dephasing is very fast, which usually prevents coherent control of the collective evolution. An excellent method for this is four-wave mixing, in which the nonlinear response of a system to four individual light fields is investigated. Project A02 developed and demonstrated a robust optical protocol to control this dephasing and the timing of photon echoes. We perfected this technique and used a total of eight light fields to capture the coherent dynamics of charged excitons in quantum dots with unprecedented precision. This established a powerful tool for ultrafast, all-optical timing control of collective quantum states in solids and paved the way towards semiconductor-based quantum memories.

A further achievement is the ultrafast electrical-signal sampling using a single QD as a highly sensitive, optoelectronic probe. We realized a sampling scheme in which a laser-synchronous electrical pulse with adjustable delay is applied as a transient bias. This approach enabled optoelectronic sampling of fast electrical transients with millivolt voltage sensitivity and temporal resolution better than 20 ps. The methods and experience gained in ultrafast electro-optical control of QD–cavity systems were used to form new projects (A10, A11, B08, C11), which further integrated fast electronics and THz radiation into nonlinear and quantum photonic architectures.

Part of our research of the CRC was the development of more efficient quantum light sources. In project B06, the goal was to realize single InAs quantum dots (QDs) in a high-quality microcavity, which allows for ultrafast electrical Stark tuning of the quantum dot. High-quality GaAs/AlAs-heterostructures with embedded quantum dots emitting around 930 nm have been fabricated by molecular beam epitaxy. The layout of the layer structure, especially the optimal position of the doped layers, was determined by simulations. Overlay electron beam lithography with an accuracy of 20 nm was established within the project.

Besides semiconductor quantum dots, polariton systems as a combination of electronic excitations and light states can also be used for controlling the light-matter interaction. In project A04, we used exciton-polaritons in semiconductor microcavities that are promising carriers of optical information because they combine photonic propagation with strong interactions. However, finite cavity reflectivity leads to polariton decay, so amplification is essential for any realistic polaritonic logic circuitry. The project A04 addressed the challenge of amplifying a propagating polariton beam without disturbing its spatial trajectory. Typically, the presence of excitons generates a repulsive potential for the excitonic component of the polaritons, which tends to deflect or scatter the beam. To overcome this, we engineered a locally elongated section of the microcavity, creating a thicker region that acts as an attractive potential for the photonic part of the polaritons. Here, we demonstrated that by placing the exciton reservoir inside this elongated region, the repulsive (excitonic) and attractive (photonic) potentials are designed to cancel each other. The result is a polariton beam amplifier that increases the intensity of the beam without changing its direction or causing significant scattering. This demonstrates that suitably combining optically imprinted exciton reservoirs with lithographically defined photonic potentials is a powerful strategy for realizing polaritonic logic elements and amplifiers.

Furthermore, in combined theory–experiment work, controlled generation of vortex modes and subsequent ultrafast control was demonstrated in polariton condensates: an additional ultrashort off-resonant pulse can reverse the rotation direction of the vortex. Using an OAM-sorting method developed within A04, the vortex state can be read out directly from the emitted light, without the need for a separate phase reference. Interpreting the two rotation directions as logical states, this realizes a transient optical bit in a planar photonic structure, controllable on ultrafast timescales. To understand our light fields in as much detail as our materials, we precisely determined their quantum state. However, this is a time-consuming process. We worked for 12 years, combining theory and experiment, to accelerate the necessary correlation measurements and their analysis. While initially a measurement took at least 30 minutes, we were able to reduce this time to less than a millisecond through consistent optimization. The strong link between project A02 and A04 formed a central link between nonlinear semiconductor photonics and quantum optics, where advanced spectroscopic methods and quantum resource theory have been combined to study nonlinear responses of semiconductor nanostructures.

Tailored nonlinearities in nanostructures and ultrafast acoustics

In several projects, we have impressively demonstrated that we can exploit the potential of our materials to the fullest – even in materials that are only one atomic layer thick and yet exhibit remarkable nonlinear effects. One example is project A06, where we explored the interaction of ultrafast acoustic strain pulses with optically active quantum emitters, a topic that was previously only sparsely investigated. As a model system, GaAs-based microcavities containing quantum dots were studied. We found that when the cavity mode lies at higher energy than the main QD emission, an incident picosecond strain pulse (ultrafast acoustic wave) can dramatically modify the emission: first, a pronounced intensity enhancement is observed, which can later be completely switched off; subsequently, long-lived modulations appear in the emission signal. The theoretical predictions agreed well with experimental data and establish a clear physical picture of how ultrafast acoustics can be used as an additional control knob in cavity–QED systems with quantum dots.

In further experiments, we investigated the control of photons by phonons in semiconductor superlattices, exploiting the giant photoelasticity of polaritons. Coherent acoustic phonons with frequencies above 20 GHz (wavelengths ~ 100 nm) are attractive information carriers at the nanoscale, but their optical generation and detection had so far been far from the quantum limit. Within project A06 we achieved an ultimate optical detection sensitivity for propagating coherent phonons in short-period superlattices designed and fabricated in Paderborn and measured at TU Dortmund. This brings quantum-limited phonon detection in extended semiconductor structures within reach. In the third period, we used these capabilities to study protected long-distance propagation of acoustic pulses in superlattices and to modulate nonlinear emission, including extensions to interlayer excitons in 2D materials. Here, we have proven that it is possible to precisely measure even the smallest movements on an atomic scale using tailor-made structures and nonlinear light-matter interactions. We have been able to detect even minimal displacements of only 100 attometres – equivalent to around one-eighth of the radius of a proton.

Nanostructures can also enhance nonlinear processes. Here, nonlinear metamaterials and metasurfaces offer the possibility to engineer not only the amplitude, but also the phase of nonlinear optical responses on a subwavelength scale. In A05, an ultrathin nonlinear metamaterial was realized that exhibits a phase of the local *effective* nonlinear polarizability that can be tuned continuously across the surface. This phase engineering of the nonlinear polarizability enables complete control of the propagation of generated harmonic waves (e.g. second harmonic) within a single, flat structure, effectively integrating generation and wavefront shaping of nonlinear signals into an ultrathin surface. The developed concept forms the basis for nonlinear holography and information multiplexing, where different images or data channels can be encoded and read out via different harmonic orders or polarization states.

Building on the expertise from project A05 on plasmonic nanoantennas and nonlinear phase control, project A08 realized the first bi-color nonlinear hologram based on specially designed gold nanostructures with different rotational symmetries. Our experiments demonstrated that multiple nonlinear processes can be used simultaneously to shape nonlinear light fields in space.

Furthermore, to overcome damage thresholds and efficiency limits of plasmonics at visible and near-infrared wavelengths, project C05 explored highly nonlinear dielectric ZnO photonic crystals. Here, we developed a novel fabrication process to realize high-quality, free-standing ZnO photonic crystal nanocavities, a technology that did not exist before. In a joint theory–experiment effort, cavity modes were fully characterized and optimized using a design-driven approach. These results highlight dielectric platforms as complementary and often superior to plasmonic ones for high-intensity nonlinear processes. Similar field-enhancement effects were also exploited in C01 at TU Dortmund, where dielectric nanoantennas combined with 2D materials boosted photoluminescence and Raman signals, measured with high temporal resolution.

Advanced nonlinear spectroscopy

Nonlinear spectroscopy of exciton resonances in semiconductors commonly relied on spectrally narrow nanosecond (ns) laser pulses, scanned in wavelength. This approach suffers from long acquisition times and limited applicability to systems with very small interaction volumes (e.g. quantum wells and nanostructures). Within the CRC we introduced a new methodology. Instead of narrowband ns pulses, broadband femtosecond (fs) pulses were used as excitation sources. Besides the wide spectral width of the fs pulses, the detected nonlinear signals remained spectrally sharp, allowing the resolution of individual exciton resonances. Importantly, many resonances can be probed simultaneously without scanning the excitation wavelength, which drastically reduces measurement times and improves the signal-to-noise ratio. This method was successfully demonstrated on bulk Cu_2O and then applied to ZnO-based quantum wells, where, for the first time, nonlinear signals from QW excitons were observed. The approach represents a major step forward in nonlinear spectroscopy of quantum systems with small mode volumes or spatially confined excitations.

Since lithium niobate (LiNbO_3) was a cornerstone material of the CRC for both classical and quantum photonics, it was important to understand the material properties better. LiNbO_3 is one of the most widely used ferroelectric crystals in nonlinear and integrated optics. Within a theory project, we developed and applied advanced ab initio methods to clarify its electronic structure and optical response. For our simulations, we used a fully relativistic modelling that include spin–orbit coupling yielded band structures with spin textures not previously appreciated for bulk LiNbO_3 . One key finding was that the fundamental band gap of LiNbO_3 is about 5.9 eV, significantly larger than widely assumed in earlier literature. Our results refined the microscopic understanding of LiNbO_3 and provide a solid theoretical basis for interpreting and optimizing its linear and nonlinear optical properties in devices.

It was known that the nonlinear optical properties are critically influenced by intrinsic quasiparticles (polarons) and defects. In project B04, the atomistic structures of the most relevant polarons in LiNbO_3 were resolved for the first time by combining ab initio thermodynamics, theoretical spectroscopy, and optical absorption measurements. The detailed microscopic understanding gained allows targeted optimization of material quality and device performance, especially for quantum optical applications requiring clean, low-noise responses down to single-photon levels.

The successful modelling of optical excitation dynamics with femtosecond accuracy represents one of the major theoretical breakthroughs achieved in project area B. In particular, in B07 we were able to successfully model the formation of bound polarons in lithium niobate. At room temperature, these bound polarons form on average within approximately 60 fs. The calculations also reveal a pronounced influence of polarons and bipolarons on the third-order susceptibility of lithium niobate. In addition, we modelled exciton transfer in tetracene-sensitized silicon solar cells. In a joint collaborative experimental and theoretical study, the complex and nontrivial effects of Mg dopants on ferroelectric domain inversion were investigated.

Integrated quantum optics and coherent optoelectronic control

Hybrid quantum networks require efficient interfaces between disparate quantum nodes (e.g. PDC-based sources, quantum dots, atomic systems), often operating at different wavelengths and bandwidths. We addressed this challenge in project C01 by implementing a dispersion-engineered sum-frequency conversion process in a periodically poled LiNbO₃ waveguide. The interface achieved an internal conversion efficiency of over 60% and a bandwidth compression by about a factor of 7.5. This combination of large frequency shift, substantial bandwidth compression, and high efficiency in a fiber-compatible platform represents an important step towards practical quantum interfaces and hybrid quantum systems, where photons from different sources can be matched to common detection or memory channels.

In the spectral–temporal domain, we engineered nonlinear quantum devices that enabled measurement capabilities beyond classical limits. For that, we developed and implemented the concept of a quantum pulse gate: a carefully phase-matched sum-frequency process that selectively converts specific temporal–spectral modes of light at the single-photon level. This device was used to tackle the fundamental problem of estimating the time separation of two closely spaced light pulses or photons—a scenario relevant for LIDAR, GPS, and interferometry. Classical intensity detection is constrained by Rayleigh’s resolution limit and fails when pulse separations become shorter than the pulse duration. We were able to show experimentally that no better precision is achievable for the considered problem. Beyond this flagship result (published in PRX Quantum and highlighted by APS), we also explored $\chi^{(2)}$ processes with engineered phase-matching for advanced quantum light shaping and efficient, noise-preserving conversion of narrowband QD emission.

Furthermore, by using backward-propagating parametric down-conversion (PDC), we explored the generation of spectrally and temporally uncorrelated photon pairs—highly attractive as separable twin-photon sources for quantum technologies. However, it requires extremely short poling periods. Within the CRC we developed a reliable electric-field poling technology for LiNbO₃ waveguides, achieving domain periods down to 1.0 μm . As a proof of principle, backward-coupled PDC sources were realized in periodically poled Ti-indiffused LiNbO₃ waveguides with a 1.7 μm period, providing fifth-order quasi-phase matching for highly efficient $\chi^{(2)}$ interaction. This poling technology enabled quantum devices with engineered spectral and temporal properties.

Besides the photon generation by down conversion in LiNbO₃, semiconductor quantum dots play an important role in the generation of photon states. Therefore, coherent control of two-level systems is a cornerstone of quantum technologies. In semiconductor QDs, coherent state manipulation had previously been demonstrated almost exclusively with purely optical means (e.g. resonant, shaped laser pulses). Project C04 showed that coherent manipulation is also possible using purely electrical control on ultrafast timescales. We found that the transition energy of a QD exciton can be tuned via the Stark effect by applying an electric field across a QD-based diode structure. By implementing a protocol akin to rapid adiabatic passage, which normally requires frequency-chirped optical pulses, by instead applying a time-dependent “electric chirp” to the QD transition energy. With our demonstration we showed that electrical degrees of freedom can be used to coherently manipulate quantum dot states on timescales shorter than the decoherence time. It significantly broadens the toolbox for controlling solid-state qubits and paves the way for integrated optoelectronic–quantum devices in which quantum state control and readout can be performed via electrical as well as optical signals.

4.1 Scientific events and science communication

Regularly, we invited speaker from different research fields into our CRC seminar series (Photonics Lecture) to present their research. Many of these events were hosted in a hybrid format and broadcasted via ZOOM to either TU Dortmund University or Paderborn University to ensure that all members of the CRC can participate. In the following, we provide a list of the speakers for this seminar series over the entire funding period:

Date	Speaker	Title
21.05.2014	Alan D. Bristow, West Virginia University, USA	Coherent Spectroscopy for Quantum Control of Matter
24.06.2014	Nitipat Pholchai, King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok, Thailand	Light-matter Interaction in Sub-wavelength Nanophotonic Structures
07.07.2014	Timur Iskhakov, Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light (MPL), Erlangen	Quantum Optics: from single Photons to macroscopic entangled States of Light

09.07.2014	Matthias Kleinmann, Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Belo Horizonte, Brazil	Tricks und Fallstricke bei der Auswertung von Quantenexperimenten
11.07.2014	Andreas Jechow, University of Potsdam	Towards nonlinear Optics with "few" Photons - Applications in Biophotonics and beyond
16.07.2014	Sabine Wölk, University of Siegen	Multipartite Entanglement: Characterization and Application
16.07.2014	Tim Bartley, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), Boulder, USA	Integrated Multiphoton Quantum Optics with superconducting Detectors
29.09.2014	John. E. Sipe, University of Toronto, Canada	Measuring and Calculating Quantum States of Light: Two Suggestions
27.10.2014	Gábor Corradi, Wigner Research Centre for Physics of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Budapest, Hungary	From crystal defects to resonant nonlinear optical phenomena: studies in LiNbO ₃ and related oxide crystals
12.11.2014	Anna Rodina, Ioffe Physical-Technical Institute, Russian Academy of Science, St. Petersburg, Russia	Theory of second harmonic generation on excitons in ZnO
13.11.2014	Elisabeth Giacobino, CNRS, Laboratoire Kastler-Brossel, Paris, France	Quantum dynamics of microcavity polaritons
26.11.2014	Roman V. Pisarev, Ioffe Physical-Technical Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg, Russia	Semiconductor spectroscopy by means of second- and third optical harmonic generation in external magnetic fields
03.12.2014	Lingling Huang, Tsinghua University, Beijing, China	Three-dimensional metasurface holography
28.04.2015	Yu-Chieh Cheng, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya Barcelona, Spain	Flat focusing mirrors: Beam focusing in reflection without optical axis
05.05.2015	Stefan Schmult, TU Dresden	High-mobility two-dimensional electron gases in GaN/AlGaN heterostructures-From basic research to a competitive device technology
25.06.2015	Alan D. Bristow, West Virginia University, USA	Two-dimensional Coherent Spectroscopy of a Semiconductor Microcavity
22.07.2015	Nitipat Pholchai, King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok, Thailand	Energy Transfer for improved Exciton Harvesting in organic Solar Cells
20.08.2015	Vladimir Korenev, Ioffe Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg, Russia	Nonlinear Properties of an Electron-Nuclear Spin System of AlGaAs Crystals in a Strong Magnetic Field
04.09.2015	Ruth Oulton, University of Bristol, UK	Coupling Electron Spin and Light Spin: The Surprising Results of Doing Cavity QED with Artificial Atoms
30.09.2015	Polina Sharapova, M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia	Quantum correlations and entanglement in non-classical states of light and atomic systems interacting with them
07.12.2015	Hui Hu, Shandong University, China	Integrated optics on single-crystal lithium niobate thin film: some recent progress
01.03.2016	Nuno Braz, University College London, UK	Towards plasmonic-enhanced tuneable second-harmonic-generation from isotropic non-centrosymmetric materials
08.03.2016	Atsushi Ishikawa, Okayama University, Japan	Metamaterial-enhanced IR absorption of molecular self-assembled monolayers

12.04.2016	Peter Lodahl, Niels Bohr Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark	Quantum information processing with solid-state single photon sources
02.05.2016	Agata Branczyk, PSI Fellow Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics, Waterloo, Canada	Customizing the joint spectrum of quantum light generated via nonlinear optics
04.05.2016	Ahmer Naweed, Islamabad, Pakistan	Analogs of Atomic Coherence Effects in Photonic Microstructures
24.05.2016	Rolf Binder, University of Arizona, USA	Formation and optical control of polaritonic density and spin patterns
08.06.2016	Stefan Schulz, University College, Cork, Ireland	Electronic and optical properties of nitride-based heterostructures: carrier localization effects in wurtzite InGaN and InAlN systems
07.07.2016	Nitipat Pholchai, King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok, Thailand	Light-matter Interaction in Subwavelength Nanophotonic Structures
08.07.2016	Xiaohong Song, Shantou University, Guangdong, China	Applications of generalized quantum-trajectory Monte Carlo Method: From Atoms, Molecules to Solids
11.07.2016	John E. Sipe, University of Toronto, Canada	The Nonlinear Optics of Graphene: Welcome to the Wild West!
22.09.2016	Birgit Stiller, University of Sydney, Australia	Phonon-photon interaction for on-chip light storage
27.09.2016	Youngmin Martin Kim, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST), Korea	Overcoming inhomogeneous broadening of III-Nitrides non-classical light sources in nano-pyramid apex quantum-dots
05.10.2016	Ian Farrer, The University of Sheffield, UK	Growth of self-assembled quantum dots, approaches to site control and novel materials
19.10.2016	Pongthep Prajongtat, Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand	Organic-Inorganic hybrid perovskites for photovoltaic applications
25.10.2016	Olga Tikhonova, M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia	Coherent control of spectral and spatial features of bright squeezed vacuum states of light
15.11.2016	Hubert Krenner, University of Augsburg	Rocking at the nanoscale: Controlling optically active nanostructures by sound
23.11.2016	Denis Sych, Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light, Erlangen	Shaped single photons: generation, characterisation and applications
24.11.2016	Shayan Mookherjea, University of California, San Diego, USA	Using silicon photonics for quantum and nonlinear optics
06.12.2016	Guiseppe Patera, Laboratoire PhLAM, Villeneuve d'Ascq	Temporal imaging with squeezed light
07.12.2016	Isabelle Staude, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena	Mie-resonant dielectric nanostructures as a platform for functional nanophotonics
07.12.2016	Yuri Kapitonov, St. Petersburg State University, St. Petersburg, Russia	Resonant diffraction gratings made by focused ion beam irradiation of InGaAs/GaAs single quantum wells
09.12.2016	Roman Pisarev, Laboratoire PhLAM, Villeneuve d'Ascq	Close relations between magnetic and optical phenomena in a complex multi-sublattice antiferromagnet CuB ₂ O ₄
07.02.2017	Alessandra Gatti, Istituto Fotonica e Nanotecnologie del CNR Milano, Università dell'Insubria, Como	Quantum properties of backward parametric downconversion
13.02.2017	Maria Chekhova, Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light, Erlangen	Bright squeezed vacuum in a nonlinear interferometer

17.05.2017	Fuyong Yue, Heriot-Watt University, UK	Nanorod structures for optical devices with unusual properties
19.06.2017	Nicolas Quesada, Macquarie University Sydney, Australia	Very nonlinear quantum optics: Generation of bright squeezed light using parametric down-conversion
21.06.2017	Gwanho Yoon, Pohang Institute of Science & Technology (POSTECH), Pohang, Korea	Metasurface-based reconfigurable visible light absorber
29.06.2017	Salia Cherifi- Hertel, IPCMS, CNRS & University of Strasbourg, Strasbourg, France	Non-ising ferroelectric domain walls: Insights from nonlinear optical microscopy
17.07.2017	Austin Lund, University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia	Quantum sampling problems, boson sampling and quantum supremacy
19.07.2017	Michael R. Vanner, University of Oxford, Imperial College London, UK	Quantum optomechanics in single photons
24.10.2017	Roman Pisarev, Ioffe Physical Technical Institute, Russian Academy of Science, St. Petersburg, Russia	Excitation of multiple phonon modes in copper metaborate CuB ₂ O ₄ via nonresonant impulsive stimulative Raman scattering
16.11.2017	Luis Lorenzo Sanchez-Soto, Computense University of Madrid, Spain	Superresolution as a multiparameter quantum estimation
29.11.2017	Susumu Yanagisawa, University of the Ryukyus, Okinawa, Japan	First-principles investigation of electronic properties of molecular crystals relevant to organic electronics materials
22.12.2017	Didier Belobo Belobo, African Center for Advanced Studies, Yaounde, Cameroon	Nonlinear wave generation in condensates with spin-orbit interaction
11.01.2018	Ursula Wurstbauer, WSI Technische Universität München	Semiconducting 2D crystals and their heterostructures
15.03.2018	Sven Höfling, Universität Würzburg	Integrated Quantum Photonics on GaAs
20.03.2018	Sergey Kruk, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia	Meta-optics: engineering optical magnetism with dielectric nanostructures
09.04.2018	Alan D. Bristow, West Virginia University, Morgantown, USA	Coherent Spectroscopy of a Semiconductor Microcavity
28.05.2018	Varun Verma, National Institute for Standards and Technology, Boulder, USA	Progress in single photon imaging from the UV to the mid infrared using superconducting nanowire detectors
05.06.2018	Nicolas Treps, Laboratoire Kastler Brossel, Sorbonne Université Paris, France	Tailored Non-Gaussian Multimode States
11.06.2018	Roberto Rosati, Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Münster	Spatiotemporal evolution of inhomogeneous electronic wave packets
13.06.2018	Jelmer Renema, University of Twente, Netherlands	Theoretical and experimental aspects of multiphoton interference
21.06.2018	Jan Wiersig, Otto von Guericke Universität Magdeburg	Non-Hermitian optics in microcavities: from exceptional points to exceptional sensors
04.07.2018	Munise Cobet, Johannes Kepler Universität Linz, Austria	Optical non-linearities from longitudinal excitons and plasmon propagation in zero-index media
16.07.2018	Jean-Phillipe MacLean, Institute for Quantum Computation, Waterloo, Canada	Direct characterization of ultrafast energy-time entangled photon pairs
20.08.2018	John E. Sipe, University of Toronto, Canada	Why you should not use the electric field to quantize in nonlinear optics

25.10.2018	Mladen Kotur, Ioffe Physico-Technical Institute of the RAS St. Petersburg, Russia	Low temperature nuclear spin-lattice relaxation in n-GaAs
22.11.2018	Dmitry V. Azamat, Institute of Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic	Pulsed EPR in wideband gap semiconductors
29.11.2018	Min-Sik Kwon, Quantum and Nanobio Photonics Laboratory KAIST, Korea	Direct transfer of light's orbital angular momentum onto non-resonantly excited polariton superfluid
17.12.2018	Vitaly Ivanov Institute of Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland	Optically-detected magnetic resonances in nanostructures of semiconductors compounds
13.02.2019	Christoph Becher, Universität des Saarlandes	Quantum frequency conversion of single photons as tool for quantum networks
13.03.2019	Carlton M. Caves, University of New Mexico, USA	Quantum-limited measurements: One physicist's crooked path from relativity theory to quantum optics to quantum information
14.03.2019	Yuri Kivshar, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia	All-dielectric resonant nanophotonics and meta-optics
26.03.2019	Robert Hadfield, Glasgow University, UK	Infrared single-photon detection with superconducting nanowires
12.06.2019	Kambiz Jamshidi, TU Dresden	Silicon Photonic Devices for Communications and Computing
25.06.2019	Marcio P.F. de Godoy, Universidade Federal de Sao Carlos UFSCar, Brazil	Functionalization of ZnO by Cadmium and Cobalt doping
27.06.2019	Igor Savochkin, Moscow State University, Russia	Magnon dynamics in iron-garnets excited by a train of femtosecond laser pulses
09.07.2019	Xiaohong Song, Shantou University, China	Time resolved strong-field ultrafast electron dynamics in atoms and semiconductors
23.07.2019	Kirill Koshelev, Australian National University (ANU) Canberra, Australia	Meta optics and bound states in the continuum
09.10.2019	Michael Rüsing, Technische Universität Dresden	Thin film lithium niobate for integrated (nonlinear) optics: Fabrication of highly uniform periodic domain structures
23.10.2019	Alistair J. Brash, University of Sheffield, UK	Solid-state nanophotonics with quantum dots
04.12.2019	Rupert Huber, University of Regensburg	Ultrafast single-molecule videography and choreography
18.02.2020	Zhiyuan Du, Beijing Institute of Technology, China	Enhanced Localized Surface Plasmonic - Resonance of Graphene Nano-ribbons
18.06.2020	Heejae Kim, Max Planck Institute for Polymer Research Mainz	Ultrafast resonant and non-resonant manipulations of optical properties in hybrid perovskites
25.03.2021	Frank Setzpfandt, Friedrich Schiller University Jena	Parametric frequency conversion in micro- and nanostructured lithium niobate: Towards the generation of tailored photon pairs of tailored photon pairs
22.04.2021	Nicolae C. Panoiu, University College London, UK	Nonlinear optics in topological photonic structures and clusters of nanoparticles
29.04.2021	Laura Vittadello, Osnabrueck University	A polaron hopping approach to lithium niobate charge transport
06.05.2021	Carsten Rockstuhl, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Duality, Helicity, Chirality - and how it's all intertwined

20.05.2021	Zhipei Sun, Department of Electronics and Nanoengineering, Aalto University, Finland	Two-dimensional layered materials for nonlinear photonics
27.05.2021	Moritz Cygorek, Heriot-Watt University, Edingburgh (UK)	Phonon effects on non-classical light generation in solid-state cavity-QED systems
10.06.2021	Robert Fickler, Tampere University, Finland	Complex Structuring of Light for High-Speed Spectroscopy and High-Dimensional Quantum Optics
17.06.2021	Young-Sik Ra, KAIST (Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology), Korea	Non-Gaussian quantum states of multimode light fields
21.06.2021	Yuping Huang, Stevens Institute of Technology, USA	Lithium Niobate Nanophotonics for Quantum: Progress, Problems, and Prospects
01.07.2021	Emma Wollman, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, USA	Advances in large-scale arrays of superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors
13.07.2021	Sonia Buckley, National Institute for Standards and Technology (NIST), USA	Beyond Moore with superconducting and opto-electronic circuits
15.07.2021	Sven Ramelow, Humboldt-University Berlin	Microscopy, spectroscopy and OCT with undetected mid-IR photons
22.07.2021	Prineha Narang, Harvard University, USA	Predicting and Controlling Scalable Quantum Systems
27.04.2022	Patrick Görrn, Bergische Universität Wuppertal	Towards Ultrafast Broadband Optical Switching Inspired by Bound States in the Continuum (BIC)
18.05.2022	J.J. Renema, Universiteit Twente / Quix Quantum BV	Integrated photonic quantum information processing
01.06.2022	Mario Agio, University of Siegen	Ultrafast quantum optics with single emitters
22.06.2022	Markus A. Schmidt, Friedrich Schiller University Jena & Leibniz Institute for Photonic Technologies (IPHT)	Optical fibers meet nanophotonics: a platform for single-virus sensing, boosting incoupling efficiencies and single-fiber optical trapping
29.06.2022	Sven Burger, Zuse Institute Berlin (ZIB)	Modeling, simulation and optimization of nanophotonic devices
13.07.2022	Christian Schneider, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg	Exciton-Polaritons in microcavities loaded with atomically thin crystals - cancelled -
20.07.2022	Ruixin Zuo, Universität Paderborn	Tracking tunnel dynamics in solids using high-harmonic spectroscopy
15.09.2022	Ermin Malic, Philipps-Universität Marburg	Microscopic modelling of atomically thin semiconductors
18.01.2023	Alejandro Manjavacas Instituto de Optica - CSIC, Spain & University of New Mexico, USA	Collective response of periodic arrays of nanostructures
15.02.2023	Christian Schneider, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg	Coupling Excitons in atomically thin crystals with widely tunable open cavities: A versatile platform for quantum - and topological photonics
10.05.2023	Iris Niehues, CIC nanoGUNE BRTA, ES	Nanoscale Optical Properties of 2D Materials
31.05.2023	Brian Gerardot, Heriot-Watt University, UK	Moiré Quantum Materials
07.06.2023	Zhe Yu Jeff Ou, City University of Hong Kong	Quantum Entangled Interferometers and Their Applications
10.01.2024	Andreas Wienke, Laserzentrum Hannover e.V. (LZV)	How quantum nanolaminates can revolutionize optical thin film manufacturing

07.02.2024	Cristian Manzoni, Institute for Photonics and Nanotechnologies (CNR), Milan (Italy)	Generation and application of ultrashort light pulses
17.04.2024	Thomas Bracht, TU Dortmund	Time-bin entangled photons from semiconductor quantum dots
22.04.2024	Ralf B. Wehrspohn, Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg	The concept of hyperuniformity in optics
22.04.2024	Zhenda Xie, Nanjing University (China)	Lithium Niobate: from bulk to thin film
24.04.2024	Bijoy Krishna Das, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras (Indien)	Distributed Bragg Filters and Resonators for Silicon Quantum Photonic Circuits
30.04.2024	Anna Paterova, Quantum Technologies for Engineering, Singapore	Nonlinear Interferometry and its applications
08.05.2024	Nicholas Gsken, Stanford University (USA)	Towards tunable photon-emitter interfaces for on-chip and free space emission control
15.05.2024	Jutta Schwarzkopf, Leibniz-Institut fr Kristallzchtung im Forschungsverbund Berlin e.V.	Epitaxy of oxide thin films
22.05.2024	Klaus-Dieter Becker, TU Braunschweig	Optical Spectroscopy at High Temperatures: LN, LT & LNT
04.07.2024	Thomas Boulier, Laboratory of Physics and Chemistry of Nano-Objects	Time-resolved second harmonic generation on Cu ₂ O Rydberg excitons
24.09.2024	Alejandro Manjavacas Instituto de Optica - CSIC, Spain & University of New Mexico, US	Polarons in motion: an excursion into defect-rich environments
05.02.2025	Helen Chrzanowski, Humboldt-Universitt Berlin	Sensing with Undetected Photons in the Mid-Infrared
10.06.2025	Gregor Koblmller, Walter-Schottky-Institute, Technical University Munich	Semiconductor nanowire heterostructures: from materials to advanced devices
12.06.2025	Martin Youngmin Kim, California State University, San Bernardino (CSUSB)	Harnessing 2D Materials for Quantum Applications and Workforce Development in AI Semiconductors & Quantum Technologies
16.07.2025	Tobias Gehring, Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Copenhagen (DK)	Squeezed Light from Lithium Niobate Photonic Integrated Circuits for Quantum Communication
18.07.2025	David Barton, Northwestern University, Illinois (USA)	Resonant electro-optic photonics for communications, computation, and sensing
10.09.2025	Carlota Canalias, KTH-Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm (Sweden)	Sub-Wavelength Domain Engineering in KTP: Unlocking Counter-Propagating Photons Nonlinear Interactions
17.09.2025	Andrew White, Quantum Technology Laboratory, University of Queensland, AUS	Better quantum science via better quantum technology

Table 1. Invited speakers for the CRC-TRR142 Seminar (Photonics Lecture).

Beside the seminar series of the CRC, we held an annual workshop with mandatory participation of all CRC members. During these workshops the project progress was presented and jointly discussed with external speakers. With over 100 participants during the last workshops, the event established itself as a well-received information exchange and networking platform among the CRC members and external project partners. The following table lists the CRC workshop series with the invited guest speakers:

Topic	Date & Location	Guests/Speakers
Opening Ceremony TRR142	06.06.2014 Paderborn	Prof. Dr. Oliver Benson (Humboldt University Berlin)
1st TRR142 Workshop	27.11.-28.11.2014 Bad Sassendorf	No external guests
2nd TRR142 Workshop	28.05.-29.05.2015 Bad Sassendorf	Prof. Dr. Dirk Reuter (Paderborn University) Prof. Dr. Thomas Zentgraf (Paderborn University) Prof. Dr. Artur Zrenner (Paderborn University)
3rd TRR142 Workshop	13.10.-14.10.2016 Dortmund	Prof. Dr. David Gershoni (Technion) Prof. Dr. Jean-Michel-Gerard (University Grenoble Alpes) Prof. Dr. Mark Fox (University of Sheffield) Prof. Dr. Mete Atatüre (Cambridge University) Prof. Dr. Alexander Efros (Naval Research Laboratory Washington)
4th TRR142 Workshop	14.02.-15.02.2017 Paderborn	Prof. Dr. Richard Warburton (University of Basel) Prof. Dr. Kurt Busch (Humboldt-University Berlin) Dr. Claudio Attaccalite (Aix-Marseille Université)
5th TRR142 Workshop	04.10.-05.10.2018 Bad Sassendorf	Prof. Dr. Alexander Szameit (Rostock University) Prof. Dr. Ulrich Hohenester (Graz University) Prof. Costantino De Angelis (Brescia University) Prof. Dr. Hui Hu (Shangdong University)
6th TRR142 Workshop	04.10.-05.10.2018 Bad Sassendorf	Prof. Dr. Mackillo Kira (University of Michigan) Dr. Paul Walker (University of Sheffield) Prof. Dr. Ing. J. Christoph Scheytt (Paderborn University) Prof. Dr. Guisepppe Leo (University Paris Diderot) Prof. Dr. Cornelia Denz (University of Münster)
7th TRR142 Workshop	28.09.-29.09.2020 Online	Prof. Dr. Rachel Grange, ETH Zürich, Switzerland Prof. Dr. Isabelle Staude, University of Jena, Germany Prof. Dr. Wolfram Pernice, University of Münster, Germany Dr. Alexander Steinoff, University of Bremen, Germany
8th TRR142 Workshop	28.11.-29.11.2022 Bad Sassendorf	Prof. Dr. Christopher Gies (University of Bremen) Prof. Dr. Armando Rastelli (Johannes Kepler University Linz)
9th TRR142 Workshop	06.11.-07.11.2023 Bad Sassendorf	Prof. Dr. Jonathan Finley (Technical University of Munich) Prof. Dr. Gerd Leuchs (Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light, Erlangen) Prof. Dr. Maria Chekhova (Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light, Erlangen) PD Dr. Matthias Kleinmann (University of Siegen)
10th TRR142 Workshop	11.11.-12.11.2024 Bad Sassendorf	Prof. Dr. Ursula Wurstbauer (University of Münster) Prof. Dr. Martin Gärtner (Friedrich-Schiller-University Jena) Prof. Dr. Sebastian Hofferberth (University of Bonn) Prof. Dr. Antonio Calà Lesina (Leibniz University Hannover)
Closing Ceremony TRR142	30.09.-01.10.2025 Paderborn	Prof. Dr. Alexander Szameit (University of Rostock) Prof. Dr. Flore Kunst (Max Planck Institute of Light Erlangen) Prof. Dr. Elke Neu-Ruffing (Rheinland-Pfalz Technical University Kaiserslautern-Landau) Prof. Dr. Ermin Malic (Philipps University Marburg) Prof. Dr. Kai Müller (Technical University of Munich) Prof. Dr. Mete Atatüre (Cambridge University) Prof. Dr. Isabelle Staude (Friedrich-Schiller University Jena)

Table 2. Invited speakers for the CRC-TRR142 Workshop Series.

4.2 National and international cooperation

4.2.1 National

Four PIs (Manfred Bayer, Dirk Reuter, Christine Silberhorn and Artur Zrenner) participated as project leaders in the federal priority program “Quantenkommunikation” of the “Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung” (BMBF). The program focused on the realization of quantum repeaters by the application of quantum optical (Q.com) and semiconductor based (Q.com-H) concepts. Via this program, cooperations have been established with Prof. Frank Jahnke (Bremen), Prof. J. P. Reithmaier (Kassel), Prof. Stefan Reitzenstein (Berlin), Prof. Sven Höfling (Würzburg), Prof. Andreas Wieck (Bochum), and Prof. Jon Finley (Garching). The work in this priority program was focused on the specific topic quantum repeaters, but the networking was very important for the visibility and development of the CRC. Four PIs of the CRC (Christine Silberhorn, Manfred Bayer, Klaus Jöns and Dirk Reuter) participated in the successor program (QR.X) that started 2021.

The Cinchetti group at TU-Do has established a scientific collaboration with the group of Prof. Claus Schneider (Forschungszentrum Jülich). The collaboration involves the sharing of the Beamline 5 at the Delta Synchrotron at TU-Do and scientific exchange on the studied systems. Beamline 5 is a VUV beamline supplied by the U250 planar electromagnetic undulator of DELTA, designed for high-resolution photoemission spectroscopy. During the second phase of the CRC, this collaboration was extremely useful, since it allowed us to perform preliminary static photoemission experiments on the studied quantum well systems.

The PIs of the Experimentelle Physik 2 at TU Dortmund have established a close collaboration with the Technische Physik group of Sven Höfling at the University of Würzburg. The intense collaboration has resulted in a large number of joint papers on several timely aspects of polariton physics, such as novel insights into interactions with optically inactive carriers and spin effects.

Beyond the cooperative projects Q.link.X and Q.RX the group of Christine Silberhorn was involved in two national cooperative projects, which are funded by the BMBF in the framework of the national program of “Quantum Technologies”. The project MiliQuant is led by the company Q.Ant, includes industry and university partners and aims at the development of quantum light sources for quantum imaging. In the project QPIC, the goal is to develop basic elements of a photonic quantum computer based on LNOI, where Christine Silberhorn and Klaus Jöns collaborate with university partners from Berlin, Munich, and Saarbrücken and the industrial partner Q.Ant. Moreover, a further project in the area of photonic quantum computing is currently planned.

Within the project B07, collaborations with Prof. Erich Runge (TU Ilmenau) and Prof. Simone Sanna (University of Gießen) were established to theoretically study the exciton dynamics at surfaces and interfaces. Similarly, in project A10 (Torsten Meier) the theoretical analysis and numerical simulations of the nonlinear optical properties of semiconductors in the strong field regime led to a cooperation with Prof. Dr. Xiaohong Song and Prof. Dr. Weifeng Yang (Hainan University, China). Here, methods developed within the project were used to study non-adiabatic interband tunneling, high harmonic generation, harmonic generation, excitonic effects, and generation of attosecond pulses.

Within the project A04 the Schumacher group has established a strong collaboration with the group of Prof. Christian Plessl at PC², Paderborn University. Within the collaboration a research software was developed: PHOENIX - Paderborn highly optimized and energy efficient solver for two-dimensional nonlinear Schrödinger equations with integrated extensions”. The software is now freely available and was also used within the projects of the CRC.

During the second and third phase Thomas Zentgraf, Christine Silberhorn, and Klaus Jöns became Fellows of the *Max Planck School of Photonics*. The Max Planck School of Photonics is a nationwide graduate school financed by funds from the Federal Ministry of Education and Research and the Max Planck Society. It aims to make graduate training in Germany more attractive for internationally outstanding doctoral candidates in the field of photonics. Particularly renowned researchers in their field have come together to pass on their knowledge to young academics. The schools act as central networking points for the future generation of scientists.

4.2.2 International

On the European level, Christine Silberhorn became well-connected with the scientific community in the area of photonic quantum technologies. Her group is participating in several collaborative projects, namely in the two quantum flagship programs UNIQORN, and PhOG, she coordinated the EU FET Open project STORMYTUNE and was a partner in the QuantERA projects ApresSF and QuiCHE. There was multiple mutual benefit between these projects and the CRC, which both aimed at the exploration and implementation of future quantum technologies. Most prominently, in CRC related topics there exist strong collaborations with Prof. Luis Sanchez-Soto (Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain), Prof. Jaroslav

Řeháček and Prof. Zdeněk Hradil (Palacky University, Olomuc, Czech), Prof. Nicolas Treps (Laboratoire Kastler Brossel, Sorbonne University, Paris, France), and Prof. Ian Walmsley (Imperial College London, UK).

Through the TRR 160 on spin physics in semiconductors there is a close collaboration between many PIs from TU Dortmund University with the Ioffe-Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences and the St. Petersburg State University. While the physics topic was distinctly different from the one of the TRR 142, there was some overlap in spectroscopic techniques such as pump-probe, higher harmonics generation etc. The TRR 142 benefited thereby from corresponding methodological developments in the TRR 160 and vice versa.

Furthermore, there was a close collaboration between the PIs of the Experimentelle Physik 2 in Dortmund and the group of Maurice Skolnick and Alexander Tartakovskii from Sheffield established, which has led to joint publications on the effects of localization in TMDCs and on the precise tailoring of the light-matter interaction in TMDCs using dielectric nano-antennas. This collaboration has been successful due to the combination of expertise in material science and devices in Sheffield and the spectroscopic expertise available in Dortmund. The cooperation was formalized by a Center-to-Center grant from the EPSRC, providing funding for the British side for extensive mutual collaboration visits.

A strong collaboration between the Zentgraf group at Paderborn University and the group of Prof. Junsuk Rho at the Pohang University of Science and Technology (POSTECH), Korea, was established and was financially supported by the DAAD for an extensive exchange of researchers. Within the collaboration, large-scale fabrication techniques for metasurfaces have been developed that also contributed to the fabrication of the metasurfaces used within the CRC.

Projects A05, B09, C05 established a collaboration with Prof. Yuri Kivshar from the Nonlinear Physics Centre of the Australian National University. Within this collaboration nonlinear metasurfaces for the application as a nonlinear lens were realized and nonlinear imaging was demonstrated. Dr. Sergey Kruk, an early career researcher from the Kivshar group, joined the Zentgraf group at UPB for a postdoctoral research period within an Alexander von Humboldt Fellowship. Additionally, a link to the group of Prof. Costantino De Angelis at University of Brescia was established for the exchange of information related to the design of nonlinear metasurfaces. Furthermore, within these projects, metasurfaces were developed together with Prof. Lingling Huang (Beijing Institute of Technology, China) to find novel concepts for nonlinear holography. The work resulted in several joint publications related to the CRC.

Joint work between the Cinchetti group and the group of Prof. Alberta Bonanni at the Linz University (Austria) has led to the preparation of a first joint publication on the characterization of micrometer-sized exfoliated flakes of the type-II Weyl semimetal Td-WTe₂. The setup used for this study allows performing static and pump-probe absorption spectra with a lateral resolution <5 μm, which was extremely useful for the study in project A08 for the third funding period.

Stefan Schumacher holds an Adjunct Faculty appointment at the Wyant College of Optical Sciences of the University of Arizona, USA. A particularly intense collaboration on theoretical many-particle physics, relevant to several projects of the CRC, exists with Prof. Rolf Binder. Already for a few years, Torsten Meier was collaborating with Prof. Xiaohong Song (Shantou University, China) on high-field phenomena of semiconductors, which has led to joint publications related to the CRC. On the theoretical analysis of two-dimensional optical spectroscopy of quantum well excitons in microcavities, Torsten Meier was also cooperating with Prof. Dr. Alan Bristow (West Virginia University, USA). Furthermore, Polina Sharapova and Torsten Meier develop theoretical approaches for the fundamental analysis of the quantum optical properties of semiconductors together with Prof. Olga Tikhonova (Moscow State University, Russia).

By combining new theoretical approaches to describe photon-counting devices with cutting-edge experimental detection systems, researchers from the University of Oxford (group of Ian A. Walmsley, UK), Texas A&M (group of Girish S. Agarwal, USA), the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST, group of Sae Woo Nam, USA), the University of Rostock (group of Werner Vogel), and Paderborn University – including the PIs Sperling, Bartley, and Silberhorn – were able to measure and characterize quantum light with high precision and despite experimental imperfections. This eventually led to overcoming the exponential scaling in the complexity of experimentally verifying nonclassical correlations of light in the transition from single-photon to macroscopic quantum systems.

Within a collaboration between the research groups of Dr. Sae Woo Nam and Dr. Richard P. Mirin at the National Institute of Standards and Technology in Boulder, Colorado, USA and Tim Bartley at Paderborn University, including travel to Boulder for a PhD student from Paderborn for three months, the integration of superconducting detectors fabricated in Boulder on optical circuits from Paderborn was realized.

The ultrafast acoustics group in TU-Do (project A06) established an intense long-term cooperation with the University of Nottingham (UK) on experimental studies of phonon-induced nonlinear optical and magnetic effects in nanostructures. Prof. Andrey Akimov a leading expert in ultrafast acoustics from Nottingham visits regularly TU-Do as a Humboldt Professor. An intense cooperation with theorists from the Lahskaryov

Institute of Semiconductors (Kyiv, Ukraine, Dr. Tetiana Linnik) supported these studies. There is also an established cooperation with the Institute of Solid State Physics – ISSP (Chernogolovka, Russia, Dr. Sergei Gavrilov and Academician Vladimir Kulakovskii) on excitons and polaritons in semiconductor microcavities.

The project C09 established a collaboration to Prof. Richard Warburton at University of Basel, Switzerland, on the topic of quantum-dot biexciton single-photon sources, which resulted in some joint publications. Furthermore, an intensive long-term collaboration was established with Prof. Tingge Gao from Tianjin University, China, related to polariton vortices at room temperature through the project A04.

5 Focus and international visibility

The CRC-TRR 142 was dedicated to the research and development of new concepts and applications in the field of nonlinear photonics. With this ambitious approach, the research went far beyond the established functionalities of linear optics and photonics. For example, the implementation of conditional optical switching functions or frequency conversion in the optical range is only possible through the use of nonlinear processes. Here, the CRC contributed to define innovative concepts to make use of novel nonlinear functionalities from the fields of modern materials physics and quantum photonics for applications in the field of future information and communication technologies. The research focus was on tailored solid-state systems that virtually connect the fields of semiconductor physics, nano-optics and quantum photonics, hence connecting several important research fields that are internationally in the focus of recent research. The impact and visibility of the CRC-TRR142 is strongly reflected by the large number of publications in the field of nonlinear optics. With a total of 380 publications and more than 6800 citations the research of the CRC became internationally recognized. This is also supported by numerous conference presentations on international conferences and workshop participations.

The extensive research in solid-state based systems and nonlinear excitations for controlling and manipulating photon states has thereby led to a new focus in the field of solid-state based quantum photonics with the founding of the Institute of Photonics Quantum Systems (PhoQS) at Paderborn University. In parallel, the optical spectroscopy has been further developed at TU Dortmund University, which led to the foundation of the Dortmund Center for Advanced Exploration of Dynamics across Limits using Spectroscopy (DAEDALUS). This research center merges the relevant expertise, the experimental facilities and the excellent equipment in the field of spectroscopy at TU Dortmund University.

